

Energy Measures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D3.1

Emerging innovative governance and business instruments to address energy poverty

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Author(s)	Sylvia Breukers (DUNE), Jordan Young (DUNE), Breffní Lennon (UCC), Teodora Stanisheva (Eneffect), Dragomir Tzanev (Eneffect), Brian Whittington (TIG)		
Document checked	Patrycja Plonka (PNEC), Izabela Kuśnierz (PNEC), Justyna Janosz (PNEC)	Date:	2023.03.21

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	BG		
	UK		
	AT		

Project Coordinator:

Dr Niall Dunphy, Director, Cleaner Production Promotion Unit, University College Cork, Ireland
 t: + 353 21 490 1969 | e: n.dunphy@ucc.ie | w: www.ucc.ie/cppu

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMeasures is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Glossary

BER	Building Energy Rating
BM	Business model
DCENR	Dept of Communications, Energy, Broadcasting & Natural Resources (Ireland)
DECC	Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (Ireland)
DoA	Description of Action
EE	Energy efficiency
EPAH	Energy Poverty Advisory Hub
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EU	European Union
HOA	Homeowners Association
MABS	Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (Ireland)
MFAB	Multi-family apartment buildings
NDP	National Decarbonisation Fund (Bulgaria)
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
OSS	One-stop shop
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PV	Photovoltaic
RE	Renewable energy
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
SVP	St. Vincent de Paul Society
TASC	Think-tank for Action on Social Change (Ireland)
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Description and purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the results of the work performed within Task 3.1 of the EnergyMeasures project. By doing so, it sheds light on innovative approaches to alleviate energy poverty in a structural manner. Workshops have been held in the Netherlands with DuneWorks and PON-Telos in the lead, in Ireland by UCC and in Bulgaria by Eneffect. Various stakeholders attended the workshops to discuss new or innovative initiatives and approaches that aim to alleviate household energy poverty in a structural manner on the medium-and longer term. In addition, and as a preparation for (and as complementary to) the workshops, interviews and informal meetings have been held with relevant involved stakeholders, so as to better understand the type of propositions that they are working on. These discussions took place with a business model canvas in mind¹, a tool to structure the discussions on how value is created for households in a situation of energy poverty and how this can be sustained over the long term. The aim of this work is to reflect on the conditions that are conducive to the promising initiatives discussed, and to reflect on the potential for replication or upscaling to other local and national contexts. In addition, this deliverable provides a background for the policy recommendations that are developed in Task 3.2.

1.2 Connections to other activities and tasks

The conclusions of this deliverable will be taken into account in the work of Task 3.2 that focuses on policy recommendations. This deliverable builds on the back-then ‘state-of-the-art’ as presented in WP1 (D1.1, D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4). However, with the energy crisis and the war in Ukraine, the policy-related state of the art needs to be updated, which will be done to the extent relevant in this report and more extensively in D3.2 that will present the energy poverty policy agenda in participating countries as well as recommendations for policy interventions. Finally, the work will also translate into the capacity building of WP6.

1.3 Organisation of the report

Section 2 starts with a brief update in view of the impacts of Covid-19, the energy crisis and the war in Ukraine, as these events have all contributed to an increase in the number of households susceptible to or living in energy poverty. We will discuss the policy responses to this crisis across EU countries. Having thus contextualised the occurrence of innovative approaches to tackling energy poverty, we continue to explain how we use a business modelling approach as a heuristic to characterise and understand the initiatives discussed in this deliverable. It will become clear that this worked out better in some than in other cases, depending on the stage of these initiatives (*e.g.*, ranging from ideation phase to implemented in real life).

Next, Section 3 reports on the innovative approaches in Scotland, the Netherlands, Bulgaria and Ireland. Apart from the Scottish case², all these reports are based on workshops (and discussions) with relevant stakeholders (see Annex 2-4 for the workshop preparations, activities, and participation). Section 4 discusses

¹ See *e.g.*, Osterwalder & Pigneur 2010

² Although not originally planned, a decision was taken to include a Scottish case study (albeit in a somewhat different format) because of the relevance of developments in the Western isles.

how the presented organisational/business models (could) work in these and other country contexts – reflecting on what is needed to sustain these models in a feasible manner in the long term.

2 Innovative governance models and instruments to address energy poverty

2.1 Recent policy changes

2.1.1 Policy attention for energy poverty at EU level

As soon as 2021, a significant rise in energy prices became visible – driven by an increase in demand due to countries getting back on track after the Covid-19 pandemic, lower gas supplies, a longer heating season in 2020-2021 and unfavourable weather conditions for renewable energy (RE). This was a cause of concern about those that had already suffered loss of income, health and resilience as a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic (EC, 2021b). On top of this, the invasion of the Ukraine in February 2022 heralded a period of even sharper price spikes, confronting the EU and member states with an enormous rise in the numbers of households in a situation of energy poverty. Next to households, other organisations providing societal services such as *e.g.*, schools, sports clubs, swimming pools, public libraries, etc. were also heavily affected by the price surges.

Since the introduction of the concept of energy poverty in the *Clean Energy for all Europeans package* (2019), some of the member states in the EU have introduced the concept in national policies. The notion of a ‘just energy transition for all’ in the Clean Energy Package means that preventing, reducing and alleviating energy poverty is to become part and parcel of national energy transition policies. Member states are required to develop definitions, measurements and monitoring methods and interventions targeting energy poverty in their National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs). The more recent crises have encouraged a broader uptake of the concept of energy poverty in national policies across EU countries, as well as the formulation of policies to alleviate the direct impact on citizens.

As part of the Renovation wave strategy, the EU has formulated a *Recommendation on energy poverty*, with guidance on how to measure energy poverty, best practices in approaches across the EU and available EU funding (EU, 2020). The *Fit for 55 Package*, adopted in 2021, builds on this Recommendation. It identifies the key forces driving energy poverty – high energy prices, low household income, poor energy-efficiency of buildings and appliances – and emphasises the need for structural approaches to decrease vulnerabilities and underlying inequalities. Various proposed revisions to existing directives call for more attention to alleviating energy poverty (EC, 2021a).

“This is not just a matter of fairness and solidarity, it is a wider societal necessity to tackle inequities that existed before the European Green Deal and that would worsen without resolute action against climate change and towards zero pollution” (EC, 2021a:5)

In April 2022, the Commission Energy Poverty and Vulnerable Consumers Coordination Group has been established. It aims to enable member states with exchanges of best practices and support the coordination of policies targeting vulnerable and energy-poor households.

The Energy Poverty Advisory Hub (EPAH), put in place by the European Commission in 2021, builds on the work of the EU Energy Poverty Observatory and aims to enable collaboration and exchange between local and regional authorities and to help accelerate the just transition of European local governments. In addition to the many resources that are available to help stakeholders implement specific actions and address energy poverty in their local context, EPAH also offers direct support through calls for technical assistance provided by a matched expert to achieve local results.³

2.1.2 Policy action at the level of member states

Member states have responded in different ways to the deepening of the energy crisis in 2022. The main types of policy measures adopted in response to the dramatic increase of energy prices in EU member states entailed direct financial support to increase household income to pay for the energy bill; regulatory measures such as social tariffs, price caps and pre-paid meters; as well as legal protection against disconnection. These measures alleviate the direct impacts felt as a consequence of energy poverty.

To provide direct relief, these measures are of crucial importance. However, they also have several downsides. Firstly, these measures provide short term and no structural relief. Secondly, they work as a financial support for the fossil energy sector. Thirdly, these measures do not contribute to a (just) energy transition, as they do not contribute to decarbonisation of our energy provision (rather the contrary). Short-term financial allowances undermine the perspective on possibilities for energy poor households to benefit from the energy transition.

Generally speaking, measures with a stronger focus on the long-term fall into one or more of three categories. Firstly, there are those directed at improving a home's energy efficiency. They aim to decrease energy-related expenditures for households through a decrease in energy consumption caused by improved energy efficiency of buildings, heating systems and appliances. These measures address part of the actual causes, namely the low quality and energy efficiency of homes and appliances (Energy Community Secretariat, 2022).

A second type of long-term measures that can help to decrease energy-related expenditures are changes to the organisation of the supply, distribution, and billing of energy to households. If more renewable energy is generated through community-based non-commercial efforts, this may result in a lower energy price and/or other benefits for households in energy poverty. This will at some point ask for a radically different organisation of our energy provision, yet when the aim is to 'leave no one behind' in the energy transition, this arguably is a necessity. The effectiveness of these measures will depend on the ways in which energy (and related) markets and energy communities develop in the years to come.⁴

³ https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/get-support/call-technical-assistance_en

⁴ For instance, there is no certainty that indeed locally generated energy supplied against cost price will always have lower price compared to energy supplied by large suppliers.

Into the third category fall measures at the heart of the EnergyMeasures project: measures relating to intermediary services provided to households in energy poverty, such as energy coaching, the implementation of low-cost measures in people's homes, and providing further personalised support to enhance household resilience.

The initiatives discussed in this report reflect these three types of longer-term structural measures: The Bulgarian innovative governance approach is discussed in view of how it may allow for the design and uptake of new financial instruments to enable homeowners to invest in renovation. The Scottish and Dutch cases are examples of energy community-based renewable energy generation directly benefitting households in energy poverty; and the Irish workshop was to explore opportunities for trusted intermediaries to make use of energy supplier funding to continue the provision of services to empower households in energy poverty.

The initial mapping of the policy responses in the national contexts can be characterised in more detail based on the three overall types of approaches described above. Table 1 shows the approaches and the respective activities and measures that fall under each approach. The workshop and resulting models presented in this deliverable all fall under one of these three types of approaches (in principle, combinations of these approaches are possible as well).

Table 1: Three types of approaches with a longer-term focus

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement		
Approach	Measure	Activity
1: Financial services to help households without financial resources to invest	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings.	Financial instruments to help invest in home renovations.
	Improving heating systems.	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.
	Improving efficiency of other appliances.	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.
2: Energy community models providing services to alleviate energy poverty	Financial support from community energy project.	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.
	Energy supply from energy community energy project.	Stable, transparent, and lower energy price.
3: Intermediary models providing services to households in energy poverty	Intermediary services (Energy coaching).	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies. Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).
	Low-cost measures.	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill .

2.2 *Creating value through innovative approaches*

2.2.1 *Background and method*

At the time of writing this deliverable, soaring energy prices, rising energy poverty and rising costs of living in general are creating concerns for national governments within the EU. They are under pressure to quickly introduce measures to dampen the most severe impact – through direct financial support, the introduction of social tariffs and protection against disconnection. While these measures provide households relief on the short-term, negative side effects are on the lure. For instance, households that are not in energy poverty often also avail to financial support measures and the partial coverage of households' energy bills contributes to keeping the fossil energy sector in place. More structural measures such as large-scale renovation and ensuring that the energy transition is beneficial for (rather than paid by) households in energy poverty are recognised as important. Yet, member states struggle to make the necessary steps forward. The mobilisation, organisation, and allocation of financial and other resources in the right direction appears to be a complex challenge for national policy.

However, national governments are not alone in addressing energy poverty. A variety of public and non-public actors at local and regional levels are taking initiative to help alleviate various forms of poverty, including energy poverty. Such initiatives often collaborate with other public and private stakeholders at the local level. It is these non-formal or not-yet-formalised efforts and their emerging models that stand central in this report. We discuss these innovative approaches with a focus on four of the countries participating in the EnergyMeasures project: UK (Scotland), the Netherlands, Bulgaria, and Ireland. Before continuing with reporting on how we have gone about this in each country, we first discuss how we understand business models in the context of alleviating energy poverty.

2.2.2 *Business modelling to address structural causes of energy poverty*

A business model (BM) is a model that shows how value is created and delivered. We use the BM canvas by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) which can be considered a seminal piece of work in the area of business modelling and is highly cited by scholars from various different fields. In our case, it will help us characterise the initiatives that are central to this deliverable. These are non-commercial initiatives that have as one of their goals to create value for households in a situation of energy poverty/vulnerability.

Some argue that a BM approach to energy poverty is problematic, as a BM cannot merge competing normativities in one model. In this reasoning, the original business modelling logics of efficiency, profession, bureaucracy, and market (profit-maximisation) cannot be combined with more collective and societal concerns around well-being and justice (Hiteva and Sovacool, 2017). We propose to make use of a BM canvas as a mere heuristic to map out the various aspects that innovative initiatives need to consider. In addition, a BM provides us with a shared language to discuss the longer-term feasibility of organisational models in interviews and workshops. Annex 1 provides a detailed description of the nine elements of the BM canvas by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010).

We can understand the actors central to the BMs that we discuss as actors with a societal mission, and the values as comprising multiple values (not mere commercial ones), and the logics around efficiency and

money-making as being at the service of those actors – not of profit-maximisation, but of enabling the sustained value-delivery over time. In what follows, we will set out how we conceptually understand the various elements of the BM canvas, paving the way for the analytical assessments of innovative initiatives in Chapter 3. Figure 1 shows how a BM canvas can offer room to address multiple values, goals and motivations that relate (among others) to energy poverty alleviation.

Figure 1 Business Model Canvas for multiple value creation (adapted from Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010)

The BM approach allows to represent the conceptual functioning of an initiative and how it creates value for a certain target group in a sustained manner (Massa *et al.*, 2017). A BM can help us to characterise innovative initiatives in terms of the way(s) in which they aim to generate and deliver value for households in a situation of energy poverty. This is relevant in order to get a better understanding of longer-term viable approaches to tackle energy poverty.

There have been several studies that both review the business model literature and conceptualise how to best characterise BMs for energy community initiatives (see Dunphy *et al.*, 2018; Mourik *et al.*, 2019; Barnes *et al.*, 2022) and BMs for new energy services (Mourik *et al.*, 2021). Previously, BM approaches have been successfully applied to map the social value and sustainability of organisational models, see for example Joyce and Paquin (2016). Rather than developing ideal types of BMs ourselves, we combine elements of the

studies mentioned to draw the contours of models that specifically deliver value for the target group of households in energy poverty.

Multiple -values, multiple stakeholders (value proposition, revenue streams, key partners and key resources)

To achieve longer-term feasibility, it is important to not only focus on value creation for the users (e.g., lowering energy bills) but also on ensuring that the organisation can continue with the activities aimed at creating this value. The cost structure is relevant because it shows how the organisation of value delivery (e.g., the costs of maintaining an effective and capable organisation; the cost of delivering value to the targeted groups) and the other costs that are involved in all other elements of the BM weighs against the revenues and if it allows for the longer-term continuation of the activities. The creation of financial value is crucial for the sustainability of most models because it provides clarity on whether the societal value can be provided in a prolonged and reliable way.

The value an initiative creates for the target group encompasses values that go beyond financial benefits. For instance, an initiative may create monetary revenues from the sale of generated renewable energy. These revenues can subsequently be (partially) used to invest in energy poverty alleviation (see for example the Energy Support Unit in Scotland, Section 3.1). Yet, there is more to the organisational models than the financial aspect because initiatives may also aim at generating, delivering and/or retaining other values such as strengthening local social cohesion; improving social resilience of those that participate; creating energy awareness; or improving health and well-being.

With a proposition that aims for multiple value creation, collaborations with other stakeholders that subscribe to (some of) these values is crucial in the design, implementation and longer-term continuation of these BMs. These stakeholders may provide support in different ways, among others, financially, institutionally, through their social networks or through the provision of knowledge and experience. Considering that at the local level public and non-public stakeholders work together towards a more just energy transition, local collaborative efforts are particularly important.

Different target groups have different needs and interests (customer segments; value proposition; customer relations and channels)

Our focus on multiple value-delivery means that the knowledge of the envisaged customers, users, and targeted groups, is important to be able to create a value proposition and to design a service (and/or products) that meets their needs and wishes (Dunphy *et al.*, 2018). The main target groups can consist of both the households in a situation of energy poverty and other actors involved, for example members of an energy cooperative. The value proposition involves energy poverty alleviation, fulfilling one or more needs of the target group consisting of energy poor households. These needs may involve (Breukers *et al.*, 2021):

- Financial support in paying the energy bill.
- Support in dealing with the institutional system.
- Support in applying for relevant subsidies.

- Support for investing in renovation.
- Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill.
- Support in applying small measures to enhance indoor comfort and air quality.
- Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.
- Enhanced well-being and comfort in the home as a result of renovations/indoor improvement.
- Experience of being able to act.
- Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness.

In case the model involves other target groups as well, such as energy cooperative members, values created for that target group may range from financial return on investments to feelings of gratification that results from having the agency to contribute to a fair energy transition.

For different target groups, different forms of engagement may be relevant. For instance, if part of the target group includes actors that invest in solutions that contribute to energy poverty alleviation, this group will have different communication needs compared the target group of households that is in a situation of energy poverty. While the former may be interested in the cost structure and in learning how their investments is used to create value, the latter group has different communication needs.

With both examples of target groups ('customer segments'), trust is an important condition of the engagement, likely to be accomplished by offering transparent, clear and verifiable information. In such efforts, key partners may provide help in reaching a target group (municipality, local social welfare organisations, NGOs or other intermediary actors in the case of the targeted households in energy poverty). Hence, a combination of local and non-local key partners may characterise an initiative – whereby the local actors involved in the specific local development and realisation are more interested in making the solution work locally, whereas the supra-local actors involved may be more interested in replicating the same solution in other (local) contexts (Barnes and Hanssen, 2022). Moreover, the targeted groups themselves may be important partners in realising the value proposition, for instance due to their knowledge and when acting as ambassadors for the initiative towards peers.

With these qualifications of the business model approach in mind, the next section presents the innovative and promising initiatives that the partners in four partner countries have selected to explore and inquire into. In the discussion of the (potential) business models, we are interested in their future potential. The way in which the institutional context (*e.g.*, existing policy; legislation; ways of doing) affects possibilities for innovation through these models, is considered – as that will also crucially affect the potential for implementation of these models elsewhere and/or on a larger scale.

3 Innovative initiatives that contribute to energy poverty alleviation

We explored and selected innovative initiatives based on partners' networks and contacts; based on the initiatives' commitment in developing approaches to support energy vulnerable and energy poor households and on their perspective on a structural and longer-term approach. Interviews have been held, as well as more informal conversations with both representatives of these initiatives and relevant stakeholders interested and/or engaged in these initiatives. A dedicated business modelling workshop was held in each of the three countries. Aim of these workshops was to collaboratively explore and clarify the value proposition, to learn how each model has potential across different (local) contexts, who is to be involved to make it work, and what sort of institutional conditions (policies, legislation, rules) are important to have in place for its continued success. The findings are based on a combination of interviews and a workshop with relevant initiatives and related stakeholders. We used the BM Canvas to structure the conversation with the EnergyMeasures partners on how to organise, conduct and analyse (the results of) the engagements with the relevant stakeholders. Although there was no plan to conduct interviews and workshops around a Scottish initiative, our partner provided us with a very interesting case description which we will start with. This initiative shows strong similarities with the Dutch models introduced in Section 3.2, allowing us to discuss the wider replicability of these models. Valid inferences based on the Scottish context could be made due to the close and long-term involvement of our EnergyMeasures partner Tighean Innse Gall in this new and innovative initiative.

In the analysis of the governance approaches in the four national contexts, we focused on the aspects that make them promising for innovation and systemic change, asking the following questions:

- What is the innovative aspect of this arrangement?
- What element of the business model does the initiative focus on?
- What are the institutional barriers and enablers?
- What is the potential for upscaling and replication?

Guided by these questions the initiatives in UK (Scotland), the Netherlands, Ireland and Bulgaria are presented in the following section.

3.1 *Community wind power to help alleviate energy poverty*

3.1.1 *Background*

In the Outer Hebrides or the Western Isles⁵ of Scotland, UK the Point and Sandwick Trust has initiated the Energy Support Unit. Under this initiative, the income from turbines of the largest community owned wind farm in Great Britain is used to alleviate energy poverty in the local community.

Energy poverty in the Outer Hebrides

Around 40% of homes in the Outer Hebrides, Scotland use all-electric heating. They are not connected to the main gas grid. 85% of homes in the Outer Hebrides (and Highlands and Islands as a whole) are in EPC band D or below, which means higher heating costs. The energy bills amount to an average of around £4,760. The yearly state pension is around £9000, and given the demographics of the islands, many are forced to spend half their income on powering their homes. In practice, those households with elderly make ups, those with small children or with people who are frail or disabled and who require additional heating, face substantial energy bills. As a result, the energy poverty levels in the Outer Hebrides Community are estimated to be at 65% of island households. The scope and scale for measures to address energy poverty can be deemed to be relevant at community level.

Figure 2: Map of the Outer Hebrides, Scotland (Ordnance Survey, 2011)

Any resident of Point and Sandwick (1,200 households across the Isle of Lewis) who is in financial need is eligible for help from the Energy Support Unit. The Trust is a membership-based organisation, and any local resident of the communities of Point and Sandwick are eligible to join, for free.

Activities alleviating energy poverty

Point and Sandwick Trust uses the income of community-generated wind power to support local social, cultural, educational and environmental development. In particular they:

- Work with local people to identify and signpost them to relevant schemes to help keep Point and Sandwick homes warm in winter;
- Deliver the Point and Sandwick Fuel Hardship Fund – a confidential, targeted hardship fund dedicated to helping vulnerable households manage their electricity and heating bills through the winter; and
- Assess the key drivers of fuel poverty in our area and make recommendations to local and national government.

The Energy Support Unit directly links income from community owned turbines to alleviate energy poverty through advice and dovetailing support – both financial and advice – to projects and schemes which reduce energy use. It addresses structural and physical conditions by ensuring referrals are made to national

⁵ The Outer Hebrides also known as ‘the Western Isles’ or in Scots Gaelic ‘Na h-Eileanan Siar’

schemes which insulate and provide efficient heating systems to fuel poor households. Point and Sandwick Trust has allocated substantial resources to the Energy Support Unit, not least in paying for a service which is staffed 4 days a week from 10.00 – 16.00.

Partnerships for expertise and funding

The Point and Sandwick Trust is a charitable organisation based in the Outer Hebrides. It is governed by founding one founding principle, to promote the social, educational, cultural and environmental wellbeing of the people of the Western Isles, with a focus on the communities of Point and Sandwick. Point and Sandwick has commissioned Muirneag Consulting, a small consultancy with over 40 years of energy, buildings and tackling energy poverty experience to manage and deliver the Energy Support Unit. Muirneag Consulting is highly experienced on energy, buildings and fuel poverty issues. For a project such as the Energy Support Unit to succeed their in-depth knowledge of the community, its issues, geography, house and household types, energy and energy efficiency is required.

The establishment of the wind farm, called Beinn Ghrideag, furthermore involved major collaboration with grants and loans from Social Investment Scotland, Scottish Investment Bank and Santander Bank. Other partners included SgurrEnergy, Engie, HBJ Gateley and Mann Judd.

3.1.2 The Energy Support Unit model

Innovativeness of the arrangement

The Energy Support Unit is a socially innovative initiative, resulting from community-led collective action. Several stakeholders have partnered to pool resources (financial, knowledge, relational, competences, experience) and join forced in order to overcome great social need. It was the Point and Sandwick Trust who built the turbines and set up the Energy Support Unit, with Tighean Innse Gall, a Community Benefit Society led by an elected community board. Furthermore, the energy expertise is directly available as well via Muirneag Consulting. Through these collaborations, a more holistic approach to tackling energy poverty is possible.

Focus on business model aspects

The model aims a providing support for local social, cultural, educational and environmental development. Going forward, the Energy Support Unit is working closely with the EnergyMeasures project to ensure local residents gain holistic support in tackling energy poverty. Multiple value creation entails direct support to help vulnerable households manage their energy bills, provide advice, make referrals to other relevant partners and schemes that can provide help. This initiative furthermore involves an example of concerted action between different initiatives, whereby an effort is made to share the learnings (on the key drivers of energy poverty in these specific contexts) with policy actors at local and national levels. Moreover, the concertation also involved that support is provided to households to apply for national insulation schemes as well as national support schemes for more efficient heating systems. Table 2 shows which measures of improvement the community wind farm approach offers.

Table 2: Services (that can be) provided by a community wind farm

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			
1.	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings	Financial instruments to help invest in home renovations.	
	Improving heating systems	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.	
	Improving efficiency of other appliances	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.	
2.	Financial support from community energy project	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.	x
	Energy supply from energy community energy project	Stable, transparent and lower energy price.	
3.	Energy coaching (household engagements)	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies. Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).	X X X X X X X
	Low-cost measures	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.	X X

Institutional barriers and enablers

Collaboration with institutional partners such a local and national government is crucially important, to be able to make use of all available support schemes, to make referrals where needed, to exchange knowledge and experience so that government schemes become better in alignment and supportive of these types of energy communities. This can be achieved regardless of the size of a community wind farm, for example, even a small 900-kilowatt turbine generates income sufficient to pay for basic marketing of available support in the community.

Potential for upscaling and replication

The initiative could be replicated by any community which has installed large wind turbines with profits sufficient to establish a similar initiative. If a local authority such as a municipality had installed their own turbines such a scheme could be authority-wide. However, for such an initiative to effectively and holistically tackle energy poverty, more than a financial surplus to be distributed is needed. This case shows that conditions for replications lie in the ability to bring together the experience base, an in-depth knowledge of the community, its issues, geography, house and household types, energy and energy efficiency. To replicate this model, basic necessities involve staffing, knowledge and experience base as well as funding for both the team and a fund for making small grants to households who face difficulties in paying for energy.

3.1.3 *Lessons from the Scottish initiative*

Approaches that are focussed on the (re-)organisation of the production, distribution and value creation of energy on a local scale for the purpose of addressing energy poverty should focus firstly on the relationship with the target group. This relationship requires the investment of time, experience and the readiness to engage with the target group and various stakeholders in informal and non-result-oriented conversations. Secondly, it should know the ins and outs of the local context. This knowledge is a key resource that requires to have key partnerships with local authorities and intermediary organisations with supplementary skills. Within the partnership complementary competences and kinds of knowledge must be present, *e.g.*, the skill to listen to residents' wishes and needs as well as knowledge on the legal, economic and procedural dimension of energy production, distribution and exploitation.

3.2 ***Netherlands: energy cooperatives alleviate energy poverty***

3.2.1 *Policy context: how the energy transition has exacerbated societal divisions*

Before 2021, Dutch national policies did not use the term energy poverty. Only with the rising energy prices, the outbreak of the war and the need to phase out natural gas, the government started to consider the nexus between energy and poverty. This was followed by measures for direct alleviation through the provision of financial support to households, followed by a temporary introduction of a price cap for household energy. In addition, funding has been provided to municipalities to organise and implement energy coaching trajectories and the provision of low-cost measures.

However, the main challenge remains. In order to structurally decrease the energy-related expenditures and to improve living conditions and health of people in energy poverty, renovation measures are an absolute necessity. Tenants in social housing, making up two thirds of Dutch households living in energy poverty, depend on their social housing association to take renovation measures such as insulation and to install renewable energy installations (Mulder and Straver, 2023). The national government has no instruments to force social housing corporations to speed up insulation and renovations. Individual homeowners in a situation of energy poverty lack resources to pre-invest in their home renovations. In addition, subsidy schemes are administratively complex, and the expertise needed to make the right choice (*e.g.*, which type of heating system to install) can be challenging, both of which effectively discourage people to apply for these subsidies. One of the main structural approaches to alleviate energy poverty lies in these much-needed improvements of dwellings and heating systems.

Without denying that these may be the biggest challenges, we want to draw attention to another dimension. The ongoing energy transition is benefitting citizens that are not deterred by the complexities of the institutional system, and that are able to pre-invest in solar PV, heat pumps, insulation measures etc. There has been a lot of discussion in recent years about the fact that energy transition subsidies and policies target citizens and households mainly benefit middle-class households. The discussion about the lack of solidarity in the energy transition is partially fuelled by local initiatives that try to change the status quo. Such initiatives experiment with ways to better include citizens with limited or no investment capacity, so that the energy transition also benefits those groups with the least resources and opportunities – including social housing tenants. These ideas have the potential to become a longer-term and structural approach to decrease energy vulnerability, as they feature a redistributive mechanism as well as the social-normative implication of more

recognition of the issue of energy poverty. Both existing and recently founded energy communities have taken up the challenge to design and implement models for addressing energy poverty in a structural and lasting manner.

3.2.2 *The Dutch energy cooperative movement and changes in their focus*

The first Dutch energy cooperatives date to the 1980s and '90s. They arose from the anti-nuclear movement. A small number of cooperatives took up the development of community wind farms, yet they remained limited in number and in their contribution to the overall installed capacity of renewable energy – to a large extent due to the unsupportive policy support schemes that were not supportive of cooperative wind projects (Breukers and Wolsink, 2007).

Since 2007, they have increased in number. Today, the number of cooperatives has increased to more than 700 at the moment of writing this report. 68% of cooperatives are involved in a PV project, most of which on rooftops. PV energy production from cooperative projects accounts for 1,5% of the total solar energy production capacity in the Netherlands. 12% of cooperatives are actively working on wind parks. The total capacity of Dutch onshore wind production consists to 5% of cooperative sources. And some 140 cooperatives are involved in the production, distribution and/or storage of heat for their local community (HIER opgewekt, 2022).

Compared to commercial developers, energy cooperatives are more inclined to engage local citizens and other stakeholders, offering participation in various ways. However, attention to engaging citizens that have no investment opportunities is not something they have a track record in. The same goes for sharing the benefits of their projects with energy poor or vulnerable groups in society. In addition, national subsidies are not conducive to the inclusion of these groups in energy cooperative initiatives. The previous and current subsidy models for collective solar rooftops are based on attracting individual citizen investments living within the post-code area of the planned solar rooftop, offering a (modest) return on this individual investment. These collective projects are based on a model that effectively excludes those without investment opportunities – even when they live under the roof on which a collective solar PV project is installed. In recent years, however, energy cooperatives have started to think of models that allow citizens without investment possibilities to participate, to become co-owners of the solar rooftops so that they can enjoy some of the benefits of the energy transition as well.

As for the various large wind cooperatives, they have established funds to redistribute a part of their financial profits. Among these cooperatives increasing attention is directed towards the alleviation of energy poverty. The recent rise in energy prices and resulting profits for these cooperatives has provided an extra impetus in this regard.

3.2.3 *Solidarity in the energy transition: energy cooperatives alleviate energy poverty*

The business modelling workshop took place on November 17th, 2022 (see Figure 3 and 4). The business modelling workshop was organised with the aim to exchange ideas and experiences of different types of cooperatives and initiatives, with the central question as to how they can best contribute to improve solidarity in the energy transition and alleviate energy poverty and – vulnerability. The assumption was that cooperatives with this dual aim – contributing to increased installed capacity of renewable energy *and*

contributing to the alleviation of energy poverty and vulnerability – need to work with a different business/organisational model compared to those that mainly focus on renewable energy generation. During the BM workshop in which five energy cooperatives, and an Energy Bank, a municipal and provincial civil servant participated (total of 10 participants), the following question was the point of departure:

As an energy cooperative that develops a collective solar rooftop (or a wind energy project), how can you do this in such a manner that you generate revenues that can be used to alleviate energy poverty in your neighbourhood/in the locality?

The participants included both cooperatives that had developed a model (and put it in practice to some extent) as well as cooperatives that were interested but still searching for ways to organise this. All participants were interviewed beforehand. The results presented below are based on both the preparatory work, interviews and the workshop itself.

Figure 3: Presentation of the Deltawind approach, Nov. 17th 2022

Figure 4: Presentation of the Zon-op-alle-daken model, Nov. 17th 2022

3.2.4 Results and analysis: potential for replication and need for partnerships

Based on the interviews and the BM workshop, we can distinguish two models for energy cooperatives that want to tackle energy poverty.

Deltawind: reinvesting in community resilience

Some of the ‘established’ energy cooperatives, e.g., those involved in wind, have set up funds which are partly used to meet various societal goals. The wind cooperative Deltawind has been around for 30 years and is currently setting up a programme to deploy their (increasing) revenues to help alleviate energy poverty. Deltawind has decided to partly use its recent profits to work with the municipality of Goeree-Overflakkee and residents to make homes more sustainable. Deltawind is investing time, expertise and experience to help residents among others with the collective purchase of insulation materials. The cooperative also helps residents to find suitable energy providers. Where residents lack resources, Deltawind can contribute financially to the investment in home improvement. Central to their approach is that everyone can participate in their own way. This can also be done, for instance, by making coffee during a meeting. At the time of the workshop, Deltawind was developing a service of an unburdening process for collective insulation for residents. In the process Deltawind took the time to sit down with residents, the municipality and stakeholders to hear what is important to them. The goal is that this project will be supported and embraced by residents. To make that possible, it is important to first take stock of what residents find important – most prominently through conversations at the people’s kitchen tables. What stands out in Delta Wind's story is the focus on developing a long-term structural approach/service that meets multiple values.

Innovativeness of the arrangement

Several aspects of the approach of Deltawind stand out. The first is the intensity and pace at which they engage with their target group and stakeholders. During times when there is a strong emphasis on the necessity to accelerate and upscale, and the urge to accelerate addressing energy poverty, Deltawind takes time to hold exploratory and in-depth conversations with the relevant actors. The cooperative takes the time which is needed for a successful local bottom-up approach, convinced that that is necessary to properly engage with the target groups and to find out how target group members wish to contribute, in line with their motto, inspired by Gandhi: *“Everything you do for me, but not with me, you do against me.”*

At the same time, a question for the cooperative is how to strike the right balance between a generic approach and customisation in working with residents (i.e., how many ‘kitchen-table talks’ are needed; how tailored is the proposition towards the residents going to be).

Secondly, Deltawind stands out through its cooperation with the municipality. It seeks to find out what the right division of roles is. The project of Deltawind is a pilot in this regard because Deltawind wants to develop a service that can be provided to several municipalities. In view of the lacking capacities at municipal level (something discussed at the workshop at length), this is an important contribution that this model can provide. Successful governance initiatives are not just about releasing and redistributing financial resources, but also about time, knowledge, relationships, experience and about orchestrating effective collaboration with partners and target groups.

Thirdly, Deltawind is also considering becoming an energy supplier in the future. In theory, this offers great opportunities to supply residents with energy at a stable, transparent and non-commercial price.

www.businessmodelgeneration.com

Figure 5: Services based on community energy revenues

Focus on business model aspects

The focus of the approach of Deltawind is on building a relationship with the target group as well as key stakeholders such as the municipality of Goeree-Overflakkee. Their proposition is focussed on offering multiple forms of value to local residents, ranging from home-improvements and financial benefits to the strong level of participation of the target group. The model’s provided values are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Services (that can be) provided by BM Deltawind

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			Delta-wind
1.	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings	Financial instruments to help invest in home renovations.	X
	Improving heating systems	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.	X
	Improving efficiency of other appliances	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.	X
2.	Financial support from community energy project	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.	X
	Energy supply from energy community energy project	Stable, transparent and lower energy price.	X
3.	Energy coaching (household engagements)	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies.	(all possible, depending

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			Delta-wind
		Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).	on specific set-up)
	Low-cost measures	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.	idem

Institutional barriers and enablers

A crucial enabler is that the municipality, but also other governmental entities such as the province, are open to a collaboration with Deltawind and likeminded energy cooperatives, so that a joint effort can result in the pooling of resources, expertise and competences. In this first pilot by Deltawind, the collaboration is going quite well. While Deltawind is an established and sizeable cooperative, with both paid staff and volunteers, there are many cooperatives that run on volunteers only. One of the participants at the was voluntary board members of a smaller wind energy cooperative (Bossche Windmolen) that was interested in using surplus revenues to invest in the alleviation of energy poverty. For them, the lack of time (no paid staff), expertise and technical knowledge was posing challenges, which is understandable: both in the approach by Deltawind, but also the in Scottish case, the importance of investing in stakeholder relations and in collaborations with key partners is crucial.

Potential for upscaling and replication

The potential for replication depends on the potential for more effective engagements between energy cooperatives with local municipalities. While energy cooperatives and municipalities are mutually dependent or complementary, overall, the engagement between municipalities and cooperatives varies a lot in terms of depth (level of trust, mutual commitment, number of cooperative projects) and breadth (type of municipal departments involved, link to non-energy related topics such as urban greening). Energy cooperatives depend on municipalities for administrative processes, bureaucratic consent, political support and, sometimes, financial funding. Municipalities in turn are hampered through their lack of personnel and expertise, a shortcoming that can be aptly addressed through the work of (some of the) energy cooperatives. This interdependence could be utilised by coordinating efforts to address policy issues that fall under the header of energy poverty, such as improved health and well-being, education and social welfare.

A prerequisite for unlocking the potential synergy between municipalities and energy cooperatives is that there is some degree of trust, recognition and alignment in goals between the two entities. The fact that Deltawind has existed since several decades is beneficial in this regard, while other cooperatives have a much less long-standing tradition. Deltawind aims to replicate this model and to share its experiences with other cooperatives so that it can be tried, tested and improved elsewhere.

Supra-local service model for local energy initiatives

Two participating cooperatives were working on a supra-local service model to support local energy initiatives aiming at energy poverty alleviation. These are supra-local cooperatives that explicitly aim at

energy poverty alleviation, and that offer expertise and support in project preparation, development and in the organisation of the distribution of revenues.

One of these, called Robin DOET⁶, has gained practical experience over the past few years with diverse projects. Their model has three pillars:

1. A professional project development pillar (technical, financial and legal knowledge, expertise and access to financing options);
2. Project exploitation/operation by a local citizen cooperative – members do not need to make a financial investment, they are intrinsically motivated, they do not participate for profitability reasons; the members of this cooperative determine how the proceeds are used and distributed;
3. A charity/foundation: to distribute the financial surplus and has expertise in this area (such as an energy bank, or neighbourhood organisation).

Through this model, a local initiative can get support in developing a collective solar rooftop, engaging citizens as members. Yet the investments in the solar panels and project development are as much as possible pre-financed based on a public loan, *e.g.*, through municipal and provincial funding. Anyone can become a member and have a say, but there is no financial incentive. That makes a difference to the conventional approaches where citizens invest and expect an individual attractive return on this investment. The business case is feasible because of the current subsidies available that guarantee a stable remuneration for the kWh produced for 15 years.

When a local initiative makes use of this service model, it means that it will not opt for individual financial returns, but for contributing to a local public good - such as helping reduce energy poverty. This can be done through direct financial support, through the deployment of energy coaches, or through *e.g.*, financially supporting a local sports club or neighbourhood centre (many of these facilities are also in a situation of energy poverty). Connections are sought with what already exists in communities.

A supra-local initiative⁷ similar to Robin DOET, operates in and around the City of Rotterdam. It is still developing its model, partially in line with the set-up described above. Both service providers consider directly supplying energy to the target group in the future. Under the current Dutch legislation this is not possible or feasible. In view of this ambition, a third supra-local initiative, that did not participate in the workshops, is interesting to mention. In the east of the Netherlands, a cooperative called AGEM is working with partners on a so-called 'local4local' model⁸ with the aim to supply energy locally to its members against cost-price. A first local pilot started recently, in collaboration with various actors including the municipality which has a central role. The aim is not so much to tackle energy poverty, but to ensure that an increasing part of the renewable energy provisions comes into the hands of local communities and municipalities, in order to ensure a price-setting that is fully transparent and based on actual costs.

⁶ See www.robindoet.org

⁷ See <https://energievanrotterdam.nl/>

⁸ For a description of the model (in Dutch) see <https://bit.ly/3G3rNKQ>

www.businessmodelgeneration.com

Figure 6: Supra-local service model for local energy initiatives

Innovativeness of the arrangement

Innovative in these models is that they frame collective community energy projects differently: rather than inviting citizens to invest and profit individually by participating in a community energy scheme, citizens are invited to support a collective energy project that benefits those that are in a situation of energy poverty of – vulnerability.

Another innovative aspect of these initiatives is their scope: although their area of intervention is the local context, their activities stretch beyond the scope of a single energy project or cooperative. The supra-local model has a larger number of projects in its portfolio than an initiative whose business case builds on one or few projects. The scaling and diversification of projects allows to minimise risks. This creates trust and commitment among public authorities and local stakeholders, increasing the likelihood of renewable energy projects being developed that help alleviate energy poverty.

Focus on business model aspects

The model is focused on multiple value creation, with a focus on creating value for those in a situation in energy poverty. While the target group still consists of households vulnerable to energy poverty, the customers are local energy cooperatives.

A local initiative, which can be an energy cooperative, but also an association of homeowners, or the municipality itself, is a key partner that acts as local initiator and intermediary. The supra-local cooperative is working on the actual project development. It is the partnership of local and supra-local that contributes

to the success: the local initiative is the local driver enabling a project. But it would not be able to carry out any sizeable project by itself because it is often based on a few volunteers and/or a social network in the neighbourhood and has limited energy- and project development-related expertise. The supra-local organisation on the other hand is reliant on the local connections and understanding of the context provided by the local initiative.

Table 4: Services (that can be) provided by BM Robin DOET

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			Supra-local service model
1.	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings	Financial instruments to help invest in home renovations.	
	Improving heating systems	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.	
	Improving efficiency of other appliances	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.	X
2.	Financial support from community energy project	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.	X X
	Energy supply from energy community energy project	Stable, transparent and lower energy price.	X
3.	Energy coaching (household engagements)	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies. Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).	(all possible, depending on specific set-up)
	Low-cost measures	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.	idem

Institutional barriers and enablers

Crucial enablers consist of the municipality, local social housing association and other public organisations that are needed as partners to make such local initiatives successful – through the provision of rooftops, subsidies for funding; support in project development; support in the distribution of proceeds and in terms of gaining local social and political support.

Financial resources to enable the prefinancing are a challenge. In this model, the pre-investment is not coming from citizens (or only to a limited extent), but is sought for from green funds. Current large financial investors such as pension funds, banks, insurance companies and asset managers are conservative and invest mostly in fossil and incumbent industries. A widening gap is apparent between the supply and demand for sustainable financing options (RLI, 2022). This is a direct barrier to the viability of this and similar models on the middle and longer-term.

Potential for upscaling and replication

The aim of the supra-local model is replication, as it offers ‘unburdening’ services for local initiatives that do not have the resources and experience to set up collective renewable energy projects easily. The upscaling is also intended to contribute to a redistribution of benefits that result from participating in the energy transition, to straighten out the disbalance between haves and have-nots that has been exacerbated by energy transition policies so far.

3.2.5 Lessons from the Dutch initiatives

Considering that there are almost 700 energy cooperatives in the Netherlands, it would seem that this provides for a good basis to alleviate energy poverty in a context-sensitive manner. Both models discussed above are relatively new, and they have been developed not thanks to but regardless of the current institutional and policy context. Municipalities struggle with an overload of work and responsibilities in regard to energy poverty alleviation, and struggle with bureaucratic systems that hamper effective interventions. National government is not able to provide sufficient and adequate support to municipalities, nor to local initiatives. The discussed models need to be recognised in terms of their replication potential. However, the current Dutch subsidy regime is not supportive of this aim. Historically, the market-based structure of the energy market in the Netherlands leaves less regulatory space for cooperatives to operate in (Breukers and Wolsink, 2007; Oteman *et al.*, 2014). This, in combination with an abundance of money to invest, yet a financial sector that is not prioritising sustainability, results in a rather non-conductive institutional context.

Against the backdrop of a policy landscape favouring vested interests, innovative local energy initiatives draw their licence to operate from their representation of local interests. As with the Scottish Energy Support Unit, the relationship with the target group plays an essential role in this respect. A good relationship requires the investment of time, experience and the readiness to engage with the target group and various stakeholders in non-result-oriented conversations. Such interactions yield the knowledge required to develop a value proposition that fits with the needs and wishes of the target group. They also help to identify the appropriate channels to propose the value to the target group, including the framing, timing and language in which the value proposition is delivered.

The supra-local service model depends on this knowledge for embedding solar energy projects in the local context. In turn it provides the expertise and experience on project development, rules, legislations and exploitation which is lacking in many local initiatives. Moreover, the supra-local model helps to create trust in public authorities through its professionalism and scale. This paves the way to the crucial cooperation with municipalities who have access to citizens, public rooftops to place solar panels on, supportive subsidies for project preparation and for other activities such as energy coaching. While municipalities have been tasked with tackling energy poverty, as well as elaborating local renewable energy strategies they lack sufficient staff and expertise to do so. Locally embedded initiatives can complement this shortcoming by tapping into the knowledge and motivation of their member base, local residents and their network of partners. It is exactly the bundling of strengths that makes these initiatives promising and that could give them a ‘competitive advantage’ over commercially driven projects.

What is needed in conclusion is:

- An increased recognition of the potential of local and supra-local energy initiatives for increasing renewable energy production capacities and alleviating energy poverty.
- Funds at the provincial and national level to support promising initiatives in this endeavour.
- A shift of organisational models from financial revenues to multiple value creation.
- An ongoing assessment of the way local and supra-local initiative can complement and strengthen each other.

3.3 Bulgaria: innovative instruments to support energy-vulnerable homeowners that want to invest in home renovation

3.3.1 Background

Political context Bulgaria: need to shift the organisation of the state renovation funds

At the time of writing, the political landscape of Bulgaria remains at an impasse. After failing to secure a ruling coalition following the Parliamentary elections from the Autumn of 2022, a new vote casting is on the near horizon. Combined with the impacts of the energy and economic crisis that have exacerbated the situation for a significant percentage of the population, the topics related to energy security, energy sufficiency and energy poverty have gained traction. Notably, the opening of the application phase of the programmes for renovation of public and residential buildings under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, has received increased public and media interest. It is on these renovation programmes for residential buildings, and how changes in the rules around the financing of these renovations, that new ideas have risen with regards to opportunities for homeowners with limited or no investment power.

Opportunities to renovate residential buildings: the Bulgarian experience so far

In the past renovation policy in Bulgaria has been very limited in its scope and success. Until very recently, the only renovation support programme for residential buildings was targeting multi-family apartment buildings (MFAB), leaving single-family homes (which make up half of Bulgaria's households) with no possibility to apply for any renovation support whatsoever. In addition, while the funding granted in these programmes amounted to a 100% subsidy/state grant, the chance of getting such a grant in the short to medium term is extremely small, due to the low speed of implementation, limited available budgets, as well as a lack of transparency in the allocation of available state resources. Early 2023, the procedure for improving energy efficiency in MFABs was launched with a resource of nearly BGN 1.2 billion (some €0.6 billion) under the Recovery and Resilience Plan, which falls under a 100% state funding regulation and can provide sufficient funding to renovate about 1,000 buildings. Currently, there are over 60,000 Bulgarian multi-family dwellings and over 1 million single-family dwellings in need of renovation. The urgency to redesign the renovation programmes to enable the participation of the excluded groups and to enable the attraction of market financing to speed up the rate of renovation is therefore high. While these plans provide at least some perspective to renovate MFABs owners of single-family buildings are left empty handed.

While politicians all too easily argue that citizens are too poor to invest, surveys undertaken by Eneffect show otherwise: there is a willingness and ability to invest in renovations, yet the administrative barriers and the lack of transparency and resulting lack of (institutional) trust is holding them back.⁹

The latest policy changes that propose a decrease in state funding during the second phase of the renovation programme for residential buildings starting in June 2023, from a 100% grant to one of 80%, offer a window of opportunity to initiate change. This happens in a situation of rising energy prices on the one hand, and energy consumption goals set out in the Long-term Renovation Strategy as well as in the National Energy and Climate Plan (update due summer of 2023) on the other hand. In addition, this change could work as an invitation to homeowners to co-contribute to that 20%, which could work to accelerate the pace in renovation trajectories as well. Not only institutional trust, but also new financing mechanisms need to be developed to support homeowners – including those without financial investment possibilities - in this.

3.3.2 *New financing instruments to support homeowners in the uptake of renovation*

Several stakeholder meetings have been organised to enhance understanding and raise awareness of the decreased state funding (from 100% to 80%) applying to the 2nd phase of the state funding programme for renovation. One of such meetings was held in collaboration with the *National Roundtable on Sustainable Energy Financing* on March 1st, 2023. This roundtable aimed among others to discuss the renovation of residential buildings. It was around this topic that the business modelling workshop session was organised (see also Annex 3).

A specific area of attention involved the National Decarbonisation Fund (NDF), which is a financial facility intended to support the move away from grant-intensive renovation towards more participation of both building owners and market actors.

Even though the national energy poverty definition is in its last stages of adoption and could provide a solution for additional support to this group, there is still no operational mechanism for financing of the participation of energy vulnerable households in the renovation programmes. Reasons for this are that mixed policy messages and media attention have caused confusion about the NDF's working, with regard to the harmonisation of the existing financial instruments and 2nd phase of the renovation programme. On top of that, there are many questions and uncertainties regarding the capitalisation and the structuring and management of this Fund. This has created planning insecurity, effectively impeding the actual on-the-ground implementation, and blocking decision-making by key stakeholders in the process, such as financing institutes, municipalities, energy consultants and service providers.

Seeing that the Bulgarian policy landscape is in a phase of fundamental changes, no specified or operational BMs in relation to the financiability of renovations could be discussed in detail. The focus was rather on the conditions the institutional framework needs to meet in order to be supportive of innovative funding schemes such as the NDF as well as the resulting potential BMs.

⁹ A decision of the caretaker Government regarding the transformation of the Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund – a dedicated financing facility with long and proven track record but limited resources - into the future National Decarbonisation Fund was adopted towards the end of 2022.

This focus is reflected in the type of questions that were discussed in the BM workshop:

- What is the interest to the first stage of the national renovation programme, and which are the identified barriers from the perspective of the national authorities?
- What is the feedback from the municipalities and the homeowners' associations?
- What are the attitudes towards the second stage of the programme requiring co-financing from the homeowners?
- Are there financial mechanisms in place to secure the co-financing, including from vulnerable/energy-poor households?

All these issues were approached within the framework of and building upon the in-depth discussion about the main areas of interventions of the NDF and the coordination with ongoing national support instruments.

The *National Roundtable on Sustainable Energy Financing in Bulgaria* started with presentation of the relevance and importance of the NDF considering the current and future national strategic goals and policies, and in view of the expected renewed National Energy and Climate Plan. The opening plenary discussed how the European Investment Bank and the World Bank respectively view the needs for an improved building renovation approach in Bulgaria, and now the NDF can contribute to this. This fuelled the discussions in the second part of the roundtable, where the main areas of interventions were put under scrutiny – namely, the renovation of residential and public buildings. In the EnergyMeasures BM workshop (see Figure 7), the potential conflicts, and opportunities for synergies in financing were detailed, with particular attention to the implementation of innovative financing instruments and the inclusion of vulnerable groups.

Figure 7: BM workshop in Sofia, Bulgaria, March 1st 2023

3.3.3 Results and analysis

The National Decarbonisation Fund: Opportunities for mass renovation of the residential building stock enabling the participation of the vulnerable groups

The National Decarbonisation Fund (NDF) is exemplary for a national financial renovation scheme that move away from the 100% state-financed schemes from past times. According to the European Investment Bank's report presented, 300-400 million BGN are needed annually for investments in energy efficiency in the building stock and these funds cannot be found only through recurrent programmes with 100% grants and a regulated market. This highlights the urgency of moving towards schemes co-funded by the households and the business sector.

During the BM workshop representatives of the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, the Ministry of Energy, World Bank, FLAG Fund, Fund of Funds and the National Trust Eco Fund contributed valuable takeaways from the discussion:

- Because there are enough alternative financial instruments, a coordinating unit is needed. It should be structured in the fashion of the existing Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund.
- The one-stop shop (OSS) principle¹⁰ should be complemented by personal contact in certain cases, due to different spread of and access to information.
- Improved coordination between institutions is necessary, with capacity-building measures at different levels of governance.
- There is a need for a large-scale communication campaign and sound awareness raising activities among citizens in order to prevent distrust and highlight attractiveness of financial participation.

During the BM session the Research Director of the Center for the Study of Democracy, Todor Galev, stressed that energy vulnerable households are eager to participate in the programmes for building renovations with own funds, despite the harsh situations they are in. However, there are various barriers to their full inclusion, such as lack of clear information, no access to tailored financial support, etc. Still, the greatest obstacle identified remains the absence of a definition for energy poverty, because a working commonly agreed upon definition will enable policy makers, public authorities and financial institutions to identify those eligible for tailored support schemes. This can increase the effectiveness of measures for tackling energy poverty and prevent the risk that those in need will be left outside of the scope. The main challenges to the adoption of a definition of energy poverty in the Energy Act discussed relate to the exact definition as well as the timing. Both could threaten a timely and operational and comprehensive definition of energy poverty.

The participants were unanimous that it is imperative to have sufficiently attractive support schemes through various financial mechanisms and instruments, including through the NDF, but that there is still a lack of sufficient information on exactly how and in what way it could support households.

The discussion also featured questions related to renewable energy, as it has been made public that amendments to the Renewable Energy Act are tabled for voting in Parliament to introduce the concept of

¹⁰ A one-stop shop can be defined as a “business model, where a single actor coordinates or collaborates with other actors in the value chain to offer comprehensive energy renovation packages” (Pardalis et al., 2022, 2). In relation to energy efficiency, a one-stop-shop can be a physical and/or virtual space where citizens can receive information on the renovation options (including EE + RES + audits) for their homes / property, in coordination with appropriate service providers and financial institutions.

energy communities, providing opportunities for people and small businesses to come together and jointly finance and exploit local renewable energy systems such as for instance rooftop PV installations. These changes may also open up opportunities for (associations of) homeowners, contributing to the alleviation of energy poverty.

Innovativeness of the arrangements

Currently, there are a number of financial instruments on the market that offer alternatives and even loans that can be paid back from the saved energy from energy efficient building renovations. However, energy poor households are practically excluded from participation in the financial instruments of renovation programmes. The first and foremost goal of the BM workshop was to advocate for the introduction of a definition of energy poverty. Another aim was to advocate for the creation of a national coordination unit on national level to facilitate the optimal utilisation of the existing resources and financial instruments. Such a coordination unit (in support of the reshaping the existing and successful Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources fund into the upcoming National Decarbonisation Fund) in the Council of Ministers is innovative in its function to combine and direct the funds available through different lines to the priority sectors. The unit would be complemented through an awareness raising campaign to shape the institutional climate towards more recognition of energy poverty and increasing the understanding of the renovation processes among stakeholders and citizens. This would stir up the immediate implementation of the necessary reforms to allow for energy poor households to financially benefit from the renovation programmes.

Focus on business model aspects

The National Decarbonisation Fund involves an increased recognition of the role of market actors, communities and citizens in financing large scale renovations because 20% of renovation funding can and must be contributed by these actors. This recognition leads to unlocking much-needed funds for closing the gap between state funding and what is actually required for renovating 60,000 Bulgarian homes in multi-family apartment buildings. This co-funding mechanism likely encourages private-public partnerships, strengthening the cohesion of public, societal and entrepreneurial actors. As Table 5 shows, the Bulgarian initiative exclusively focusses on financial instruments to stimulate renovations.

Although an institutionalised definition of energy poverty is still absent, the acknowledgement that households and families without pre-investment opportunities are a target group in their own right can be considered progress. It holds the potential that households in energy poverty develop more trust in schemes that try to offer support in their situation.

Table 5: Services (that can be) provided by new financing models enabled by NDF

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			NDF
1.	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings	Financial instruments to help invest in home renovations.	X
	Improving heating systems	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.	

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			NDF
	Improving efficiency of other appliances	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.	
2.	Financial support from community energy project	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.	
	Energy supply from energy community energy project	Stable, transparent and lower energy price.	
3.	Energy coaching (household engagements)	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies. Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).	
	Low-cost measures	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.	

Institutional barriers and enablers

Several reforms and immediate actions have been identified (related to structural/institutional barriers and potential):

- Introduction of energy poverty definition – a crucial reform that is still absent and will have a significant impact on all major energy and climate strategic goals, and most importantly, will allow for the participation in the building renovation programmes of a significant number of the population.
- Gradual lowering of the grant component for building renovation under the national programmes
- Dedicated communication and awareness raising campaign.
- Availability of training and capacity building for local actors involved in energy and climate actions on the local level, especially in the management and implementation of building renovation policies and measures.

Potential for upscaling and replication

At the national level, enabling the successful functioning of National Decarbonisation Fund – *e.g.*, through the proposed national coordination unit - can open up space for effective policy instruments and financing programmes in support of the building renovation. Increased interest towards financing of energy efficiency programmes is expected to benefit the energy service companies' market, local funds and micro-crediting institutions. The pay-as-you save schemes as well as the one-stop-shop model need further elaboration to enable a comprehensive approach that reaches actors across the entire value-chain of energy efficiency building renovation projects, down to homeowners' associations and citizens. Although not discussed in detail in the workshop, pay-as-you save schemes have potential to be successful for the support of energy poor households, too, as in principle they are investments in cost-effective efficiency upgrades that can improve the living conditions, reducing energy bills – investments that can be recovered over time by the

users (households). The one-stop-shop model, on the other hand, is flexible in practice, and can entail different business models depending on the needs of a particular municipality, providing consultation and expert advice upon demand to all citizens.

In terms of replicability, there is significant potential, when local positive experiences with financial instruments are shared and implemented more broadly. Both the national coordination unit, as well as an organisation as Eneffect can play a role in the exchange of experiences and the upscaling of best practices.

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Figure 8: Innovative financial schemes for energy vulnerable citizens

3.3.4 Lessons from the Bulgarian initiative

The emergence of innovative governance arrangements allowing Bulgarian citizens and businesses to co-fund the renovation of the building stock takes place against the backdrop of fundamental policy changes at a national level. The move away from complete state funding places new issues on the policy agenda. First of all, a shared definition of energy poverty which helps to tailor measures towards the needs of the target group, is needed. Second, businesses and households need to be made aware of these new opportunities for co-funding. Third, an improvement of institutional trust is crucial to encourage these private actors to take on a role and make use of new opportunities. These issues can be seen as fundamental points of departure from where onward viable and effective business models for scaling up building renovations can develop. As part of that generic effort, additional attention is needed for potential BMs that help address energy poverty,

through financial support mechanisms for private homeowners to be able to co-invest in the renovation of their home.

The institutional transformation discussed is such an early phase that such business models as well as the accompanying new modes of collaboration, have not yet been developed and discussed in detail. Hence, rather than new business models, the workshop in Bulgaria has resulted in a clarification of the underlying operating principles for promising initiatives which could be derived through discussions of relevant stakeholders during the workshop. These principles are summarised in the BM canvas (see Figure 8). Hence, BMs could be organised around one-stop-shop principles, offering homeowners and/or HMOs all information, advice and required contacts at one trusted point of access instead of being distributed across several departments and levels of governance. Another approach highlighted in the discussions was that of offering renovation and energy-improvement services on a pay-as-you save basis. This could be especially relevant for including energy vulnerable households, as it offers them the opportunity to benefit from renovations without having to pre-invest.

Instead of concrete business models, the most significant development in the Bulgarian context is the institutional transformation taking place at a national policy-making level. Through the development of more favourable regulatory conditions, new governance models and modes of cooperation between public and private entities that strive to alleviate energy poverty can be provided with a fertile ground. In conclusion, the institutional changes in Bulgaria open up space for addressing energy poverty in a more coordinated, collaborative and recognised manner.

3.4 Ireland: new private-public partnerships

3.4.1 Policy context: Recognition for the issue of energy poverty

Energy poverty in Ireland has been considered a recognisable political imperative for several decades, with political and policy cycles coalescing around providing social supports to energy vulnerable households as far back as the 1940s. More recently, Ireland was one of the first member states to have energy poverty placed firmly in the policy cycle; establishing an Energy Poverty Advisory Group advises the government's Department of Communications, Energy, Broadcasting and Natural Resources (DCENR) on the topic. Recent government publications include working definition of energy poverty, which is accepted as "*a persistent and complex social, environmental, and political phenomenon and is not unique to Ireland*" (Lawlor and Visser 2022:1).

2022 saw the government's Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC) introduce an updated strategy and action plan to tackle the issue (DECC, 2022b; 2022a); and while Ireland has had some degree of success rolling out onshore wind, oil continues to take up the largest share of residential energy demand, accounting for 41% of all home energy use in the state. In terms of electricity, oil and natural gas still account for 25% and 19% respectively (SEAI, 2022). Ireland's dependency on natural does not leave it immediately vulnerability to the ongoing war in Ukraine, given it does not directly import natural gas from Russia, it has had to react to the knock-on effects to the international gas pricing (O'Connell, 2022).

A notable recent development in Ireland has been the introduction of the one-stop shop (OSS) concept for home energy grants by The Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI). SEAI is the state body established to promote and help develop sustainable energy infrastructure in Ireland and is playing a critical role in state's energy transition, particularly through its regulation of national grants designed to improve the energy efficiency of the country's building stock. Through its OSS service it offers homeowners all the retrofitting services required for a complete home energy upgrade, linking them to registered private operators that will manage the entire process – from the initial assessment of the home, through to the upgrade work carried out, and finally the BER¹¹ certification.

While this has had a significant positive impact in encouraging private building owners to retrofit/upgrade their homes, it has had some unintended consequences to the business model viability of some third sector actors that have traditionally provided energy poverty supports to vulnerable communities. An example of its impact can be read in Section 3.4.3 of this deliverable. Another criticism of the service is that it tends to favour those in society who can afford to carry out the retrofitting work. With projects often coming in at €40,000 or more, the SEAI grants cover up to 50% of the cost, with the remainder of the costs involved fall to the homeowner. The promised matching low-interest loan scheme (also to be administered by the SEAI) has yet to materialise and has resulted in a certain asymmetry forming in favour of those who can afford to absorb the burden of outstanding costs involved. For a more detailed assessment of the policy situation in Ireland see Breukers *et al.* (2021).

3.4.2 Intermediaries addressing energy poverty

The role of third sector¹² actors like NGOs, partnership companies, charities, etc., in Ireland is to develop interlinkages between public and private institutions, while at the same time adhere to the interests of the clients they represent. A key characteristic of this sector is as follows (Benefacts, 2018:4):

Ireland's nonprofit sector has more than 29,000 entities that are independently governed, autonomous of Government, constituted on a not-for-profit basis and whose purposes are for public (rather than private) benefit.

In addition, third sector actors like those mentioned below very often have a policy dimension to their work and where possible try to effect change through campaign and advocacy work, both within the public domain but also with decision makers more directly. This work also allows for decision makers and policy actors to gain reliable systematic intelligence on specific topics of interest, albeit from actors motivated by public benefit. Consequently, the potential to influence the policy cycle can be quite good. Though this does depend on the human and financial resources available to specific third sector actors. Additionally, Ireland's third sector provides a substantial social economy within the broader economy, directly employing some 165,000 people, and managing an income of some €14.2bn per year, with these organisations raise over half of this

¹¹ The Building Energy Rating (BER) certificate certifies a (domestic) building's energy performance rating on a scale from A to G with A-rated homes classed as being the most energy efficient.

¹² Also referred to as the non-profit or voluntary sector, and sometimes the community development sector depending on which entity is being discussed.

income (more than €8.3bn) themselves, majorly subsidising the cost of public services in Ireland (The Wheel, 2022). Their most recent report on the topic, the Irish Charities Regulator, estimate these figures as far higher with a combined direct, indirect and induced expenditure of €24.98 billion for the sector, supporting 289,197 employees (Charities Regulator, 2018). While the Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant detrimental effect on the sector's ability to raise funding, with 55% of respondents from the sector reporting finances as "uncertain or in difficulty" in 2020 (Charities Regulator, 2020) the sector still plays a significant role in Irish society, which in turn impacts decision-making in the Irish policy cycle.

While this role can be significant, it does not mean that third sector actors are immune to the changes in the direction of policy making in Ireland. Third sector actors can sometimes be victims of their own campaigning successes. For example, with the introduction of the 2022 Climate Action Bill, new targets were set for retrofitting 500,000 homes by 2030. This shift in emphasis to far deeper retrofitting of building stock, coupled with the introduction by the SEAI of its one-stop-shop programme has had a significant knock-on effect for third sector actors providing insulation and more minor retrofitting services to energy vulnerable households. Third sector actors, who were once able to leverage government employment support services to upskill and train lower-skilled and/or underemployed workers to do the work suddenly found that they could no longer provide a cost-effective service given the new emphasis on having higher-skilled, SEAI-registered contractors¹³ do the work instead. Therefore, the multi-factor (multiple benefit) approach taken by third sector actors found themselves significantly impacted by unintended consequences of seemingly sensible changes in policy. Changes in the policy cycle like this can rapidly impact the business models of third sector actors, making what was once a manageable and effective business model suddenly become unviable. Looking at one third sector as an example, their business model involved leveraging different government supports and funding streams to meet their outgoing costs, especially those relating to home insulation material and personnel¹⁴. While the material benefit is somewhat self-explanatory, the training aspects to their work had significant added societal benefit to those living in the communities they operated in. Past workers (many of whom were themselves living in energy poverty) received training and developed a deeper understanding of the energy performance of their own homes and the steps needed to carry out remedial work. In addition, new employment opportunities became available to them with all the associated positive knock-on effects this would have for themselves and their friends and neighbours.

3.4.3 *Search for new models enabling third sector organisations to help alleviate energy poverty*

Considering the recent change in the landscape set out above, the question has risen how third sector organisations can 're-invent' themselves and find models that could work well in this new reality. While the Climate Action Bill and the SEAI's OSS approach has been a welcome development for the broader Irish society, it has had a negative impact on ability of some in the sector to support energy vulnerable households. Criticism, particularly in relation to the rigidity of the rules on only using SEAI approved/registered

¹³ Using contractors not on the SEAI register would automatically lead to the homeowner being disqualified from receiving the associated grants made available by SEAI.

¹⁴ Personnel were cycled in and out of projects through apprenticeship-style training, whereby staff that had upskilled and been trained to effectively carry out retrofitting work would move on (taking up new, higher skilled roles in the construction sector), leaving space to recruit newer less skilled staff to replace them.

contractors has actually resulted in increases to overall construction/retrofitting costs with any savings designed to go to the consumer actually being swallowed up by the contractor rather than being passed on. This has in turn made it more difficult for energy vulnerable households to make even minor improvements to their homes due to the associated rising costs of material and labour in the construction sector. According to Friends of the Earth Ireland (2023) domestic energy efficiency programmes have been limited by a low uptake among lower income households due to a dearth in accessible and trustworthy information, ineligibility due to overly strict and arbitrary rules, or because of competing priorities. As McCarthy and Harris (2021, 3) note: “[A] lack of access to finance is considered a key barrier for low-income households to invest in energy efficiency measures”.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the issues involved and to start a conversation with third sector actors involved in tackling energy poverty, a BM workshop (supplemented by individual engagements) was organised, to which a variety of third sector intermediary organisations were invited (see Annex 4 for more information on the workshop set-up and participants). Participants to the workshop included the Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (MABS); ALONE, a charity organisation in Ireland advocating on behalf of older people living alone; TASC (Think-tank for Action on Social Change); and St. Vincent de Paul Society (SVP) Ireland, an international Christian voluntary network dedicated to tackling poverty in all its forms. In addition, Energy Action (a former partner in EnergyMeasures) participated in this workshop that was facilitated by UCC.

The workshop discussions were broken down into themes, focusing on the different scales of action that these organisations work on: from the national structural level, to the short- and medium-term policy cycles, to immediate day-to-day barriers each organisation faces. Also, the organisers wanted to both highlight the novel and innovative approach that Energy Action was working on to leverage emerging social benefit funds being made available by Irish energy providers, prior to its cessation, and to explore avenues for cross collaboration that may not have been immediately obvious to those invited organisations. During the workshop, the following questions were central to achieving these goals through detailed discussion:

- How do we address the structural and physical conditions of energy poverty?
- What can we do (in the short and medium term) to address energy poverty?
- How is your organisation working to meet the challenge of energy poverty and what are the key challenges you face implementing it?

In answering these questions, one of the participants highlighted low income and the poor condition of existing housing being key to the structural and physical conditions of energy poverty. There was agreement that government efforts are not adequately addressing these factors, confirming the Friends of the Earth Ireland’s report mentioned above. The policy shift to deeper retrofit, while widely appreciated and accepted as appropriate, has not resolved the issues facing those in energy poverty and who engage with them. Therefore, there need to be more targeted, hands-on approaches from government (*e.g.*, schemes specifically targeting the energy vulnerable and supported by more specific SEAI grants). Also, existing rules in place are not streamlined to target energy vulnerable and when supports are in place the rules can be quite arbitrary leading to energy vulnerable not benefiting or even being penalised. Again, participants were in agreement with the literature that rules currently in force for qualifying for grants etc. (while quite rightly

designed to minimise abuse of the system) unfairly locked out low-income and energy vulnerable users from participating.

While all the organisations present at the BM workshop operate client-centred models for engaging energy vulnerable households, they sometimes place particular emphasis on specific cohorts. For example, ALONE's clients are in the main retirees and older householders. MABS and SVP both focus on supporting clients from all cohorts but acknowledge that they don't always get to engage all clients in need due to certain internal limitations and certain societal externalities. MABS, for example has over 100 applications per week to assist clients with the four main energy providers in Ireland.¹⁵ They estimate approximately 85% of their work is with fuel suppliers and access to hardship funds. They also indicated that the electricity providers have varying levels of funding available to assist vulnerable customers that predate the current energy crisis. These can range from a once-off payment of €50 to between €2,000 and €3,000 of write-offs from accrued bills.

Figure 9: Participants contributing to the workshop in Dublin, January 30th, 2023

3.4.4 Results and analysis

From our analysis of the interviews and outcomes from the BM workshop, we have identified a novel, potentially innovative, public private partnership (PPP) programme that can be integrated into the existing business models of third sector actors or as part of a standalone model that can be utilised to specifically tackle the energy poverty issued of their clients:

Energy Action's Public Private Partnership initiative

Third sector actors, particularly those operating as charities, can often struggle with maintaining stable revenue streams to carry out their operations. Therefore, charities very often must source or generate income from multiple revenue streams, *e.g.*, government funding, grant aid supports, donations, and increasingly with private sector actors in a type of PPP arrangement. An example from Korea, the *Seoul Energy Welfare Public-Private Partnership Program* has been in operation since 2015 engaging at-risk communities in the city, carrying out much needed home energy efficiency upgrades, providing targeted job

¹⁵ For more information on the market share for each of the domestic electricity suppliers operating in Ireland in 2020, see: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/753319/domestic-electricity-market-share-of-customers-in-ireland/>

training and employment supports, while also securing innovative and sustainable financing arrangements focusing on long term sustainability. This sustainably financed model for alleviating energy poverty has three key criteria for success, including:

“Environmental Benefits – Around 1,600 micro-PV panels have been installed at public apartments and low-income houses in disadvantaged communities under the program.

Social Benefits – Fifty former energy consultants and energy social workers are continuing work in the industry, having founded eight cooperatives and four non-profit organisations.

Economic Benefits – The virtual power plant registered under the project has resulted in annual profits of more than \$180,000 [approximately ₩36,077,647 (KRW)] sent to the Seoul Energy Welfare Civic Fund.”

(C40 Cities, 2016)

Similarly, in Ireland, Energy Action had identified a new income stream emerging from a number of Ireland’s energy providers looking to partner with third sector actors on reciprocal, common purpose projects, where they would make funding available, and the third sector actor would work with them to identify and engage energy vulnerable clients who also happened to be customers of the energy provider.

Innovativeness of the arrangement

This type of public-private partnership approach is quite new in Ireland and can be seen as part of the wider shift towards incorporating energy justice aspects to the energy transition. It also suggests how third sector actors might leverage their existing institutional strengths to identify and develop new synergies with traditional energy market actors that go beyond simple customer-oriented arrangements. Unfortunately, for Energy Action this innovation did not impact the wider structural pressures they faced and, in the end, did not prevent it from having to cease operating (due in part to the policy shift prioritising deep retrofit explained earlier). However, during the BM workshop the other third sector participants recognised the potential this arrangement could have to their own operations.

Focus on business model aspects

The focus of Energy Action’s approach, much like Deltawind described above, was to leverage the considerable institutional knowledge the charity had built up over the years and having developed strong relationships based on trust with their clients, to reach out to key stakeholders in local government and the energy providers operating in the Dublin area. Their proposition to those stakeholders was to use the potential income from the energy companies to offer multiple forms of value to their clients, ranging from home-improvements, employment training supports, and the installation of new technologies (in the form of heating controls) in the client’s home. These heating controls were combined with a (free to the client) annual service associated with the heating controls and the provision of (again free to the client) a set electricity allowance that participating clients could avail of during off-peak periods¹⁶. The benefit to the third

¹⁶ A particularly innovative part of this arrangement was the utilising of the proportion of renewable electricity currently entering the grid that is not accounted for in existing feed-in tariff arrangements or other pricing schemes.

sector actor, in addition to the income stream was the aligning of existing services they provide to novel services and allowances not previously available to their clients. While the benefit to the electricity provider was in their ability to link their societal benefit obligations to tangible projects operated by third sector actors that were trusted by the target group. Table 6 summarises the areas in which the Irish model aims to create improvements.

Ireland's policy position on energy poverty is quite developed, although there has been a tendency to prioritise financial supports rather than tackle the systemic causes of energy poverty. As such, the value proposition of this type of business model for third sector actors was instantly recognised by participants in the BM workshop.

Table 6: Services (that can be) provided by the intermediary service model

Value provision aimed at structural and long-term improvement			Intermediary service model
1.	Renovation/improving energy efficiency of dwellings	Leveraging existing financial instruments to help invest in home renovations (<i>i.e.</i> , shallow retrofit).	X
	Improving heating systems	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of new heating systems.	X
	Improving efficiency of other appliances	Financial instruments to improve the affordability of appliances.	X
2.	Financial support from community energy project	Financial support in paying the energy bill. Support in investing in renovation.	X
	Energy supply from energy community energy project	Stable, transparent and lower energy price.	X
3.	Energy coaching (household engagements)	Support in dealing with the institutional system. Support in applying for relevant subsidies. Support in understanding the energy contract, energy bill. Support in tackling other (related) problems such as indebtedness. Experience of being able to act (resilience). Technical and behavioural advice. Referrals to national subsidies and schemes (renovation and heating systems).	(all possible, depending on specific set-up)
	Low-cost measures	Support in applying small measures enhance indoor comfort and air quality. Support in applying small measures to decrease the energy bill.	idem

Institutional barriers and enablers

A crucial enabler in this case are the electricity providers giving access to the funding required to carry out the associated services. This arrangement however is potentially vulnerable to changes in personnel (and the associated potential loss in trust between the stakeholders involved) or changes in the financial priorities (*e.g.*, no longer prioritising societal benefit programmes within the institution) of the energy company providing the funding.

Potential for upscaling and replication

Therefore, the long-term sustainability of this kind of model would need to see the establishment of legal frameworks whereby the monies made available by the energy companies were clearly defined as an associated operating cost of the company involved. The establishment into law of ‘societal benefit’ as a key performance indicator for energy companies could be one avenue for improving the potential for upscaling and replication, but existing legal and financial parameters would need to be addressed before this could happen.

Figure 10: Intermediary service model

3.4.5 Lessons from the Irish initiative

In Ireland we see that a policy shift to deeper retrofit, while in theory an appropriate measure to make more serious work of tackling an important structural cause of energy poverty, has not resolved the issues of those residents living in energy poverty and those who engage with them. The provided support measures are insufficiently accessible for households in energy poverty due to complexities and financial thresholds. On top of that third sector organisations that work with these households have been pushed into the margins. The historically strong role of third sector organisations is under threat and that could have multiple impacts. With Energy Action and similar organisations discontinuing their work, a valuable and indispensable

connection to households in a situation of energy vulnerability and poverty is lost. This adds to the asymmetrical support that the OSS offers – benefiting those households that can afford to invest in their home improvements while losing sight of large numbers of households that cannot.

With these organisations discontinuing their activities, budgets and jobs are also lost. Fewer people from the targeted groups find employment through support programmes because the SEAI-registered contractors are the ones that provide the services instead. This means that contractors increasingly are out-of-touch with the lived experiences and realities of households in energy poverty.

An unintended effect of the Irish national governance approach to energy poverty therefore is a decrease in access to trusted and close-by intermediaries that provide support against no or low costs which was previously available. Together with a direct lack of access to finance, this is withholding low-income households from investing in improving the energy efficiency of their homes.

Third sector organisations are however not giving up, and actively explore new partnerships with energy suppliers who are by legislation required to spend money on energy poverty alleviation. Through these efforts, the contours of a new model have emerged. New revenue streams derive from a number of Ireland's energy providers who are interested in partnering with third sector actors, recognising the value these organisations have in identifying, engaging with and offering tailored support to energy vulnerable households. Third sector actors see opportunities to re-invent themselves, leverage their existing institutional strengths (knowledge, know-how, relationships of trust with households, and with other local stakeholders) to set up new arrangements with traditional energy market actors - beyond simple customer-oriented arrangements. Important for this model to work well on the longer term is that the availability and direction of funding is ensured, through legal framework changes.

The third sector in Ireland is dynamic and resilient, yet not to an endless extent. While new forms of PPPs may work out well, their longevity depends on institutional embedding and recognition. And for this recognition to occur, the crucial added value and potential of third sector organisations to alleviate energy poverty must be recognized by policy makers at the national level.

4 Conclusion and discussion

4.1 Novel initiatives

The aim of this report is to explore the potential of innovative governance initiatives in alleviating energy poverty. The preceding sections have presented and offered a reflection on such initiatives in four partner countries of the EnergyMeasures project, namely Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands and the UK (Scotland) (see Table 7). The analysis was based on interviews, workshops, and/or the direct involvement of partners in these initiatives. A business modelling approach was used as a heuristic to structure the discussions and analysis. Main conditions for innovative initiatives that alleviate energy poverty in a structural and long-term manner, is that they are able to expand, entrench or further embed their approach in order to be able to replicate or upscale efforts – or to inspire and support others to replicate their models. To be able to do so, sufficient resources (financial, knowledge, skills, human, relational) are crucial and as presented there is a lot of creativity in the ways in the efforts to secure those resources.

The models presented for Scotland and the Netherlands were examples of community-based renewable energy generation directly benefitting households in energy poverty. The Bulgarian innovative governance examples discussed were still in the very early stages, enabled by important changes that are underway at the national policy level – inviting the development of new financial instruments to enable homeowners to help realise renovations. The Irish chapter addressed the importance of trusted intermediaries and third sector organisations and presented a model that can help ensure their continued ability to work with and for households in energy poverty, pointing out that in order for them to do so, a more secure stream of funding, such as the one from energy suppliers, is essential.

Table 7: Examples of models for multiple value provision as discussed

Type of approach	Examples
Financing services to households to enable uptake of improvements to the energy efficiency of buildings, heating systems and appliances	Bulgaria: National policy change which paves the way for the design and uptake of new financial instruments to enable homeowners without financial resources to invest in renovation.
Energy-community based services to help to decrease energy-related expenditures, through changes to the organisation of the supply, distribution and billing of energy to households	Scotland and the Netherlands: Models to combine energy community-based renewable energy generation with direct support for households in energy poverty (with future possible direct RE supply to households)
Intermediary services provided to households in energy poverty	Ireland: private-public-partnership model that enables trusted intermediaries to provide support to households in energy poverty using energy suppliers' funds

4.2 Stakeholder alignment, pooling resources and reciprocity

In the Scottish, Dutch, Irish and Bulgarian cases, the alignment of stakeholders at different levels is a crucial element for successful deployment of activities. For instance, the Dutch supra-local service provision model aims to complement knowledge and connections of local initiatives. Yet the supra-local service provider has expertise and experience in project development, rules, legislation and connections to national policy – which local initiatives lack. Moreover, the supra-local model helps to create trust from the side of public authorities through its professionalism and scale. This paves the way to the necessary collaboration with municipalities and local authorities that on their turn have access to resources that the service provider lacks, ranging from access to citizens, public rooftops for solar PV and subsidies to knowledge on local spatial planning and support). Hence, a mutually beneficial and reciprocal collaboration can emerge that is conducive to tackling energy poverty – which remains central through statutory anchorage. In this collaboration, smaller locally embedded initiatives can complement resources based on their knowledge of and alignment with local residents and their network of partners. In the Scottish case, the mutual alignment between organisations that operate at different levels has worked as a flywheel in terms of providing value to households in energy poverty.

For the Irish model, the intermediary position of third sector organisations with their proximity to the target groups and mature and trusted relationships with other partners is a crucial strength. In Bulgaria, municipalities and organisations such as Eneffect are actively building networks for raising awareness about the opportunities that new funding schemes have for home owner associations of multi-family apartment buildings as well as the benefits for their residents. Through such communication campaigns knowledge and trust among housing owners is increased. This accelerates the adoption of energy efficiency renovations and leads to the improvement of the housing and financial conditions for energy vulnerable households.

Collaboration across sectors, involving public and private actors, citizens, volunteers and (stakeholders that work with) the targeted group is characteristic of the innovative models discussed above. Each context has its own specificities depending on the relations with key actors such as the municipality, the availability of volunteers and socially oriented staff members, their connections to relevant market and energy sector actors. For the Scottish, Dutch and Irish models, this means that the people that drive these initiatives need to be flexible and capable of engaging and interacting with a diverse set of actors. Building a network of trusted actors, being able to bring partners together around a shared or common goal, whereby collaboration rather than competition is the norm, is key. The Bulgarian case is special in this respect because the national policy reforms open up space for new forms of collaborations to emerge, for instance between market actors and home owner associations and between NGOs and governmental agencies. A definition and understanding of energy poverty that is shared by a large array of stakeholders carries large potential to further unify actors from different sectors and levels who are trying to find solutions for its alleviation, and complement each actor's respective resources and mandate.

The orchestration of human resources enabled by networks allows for a bundling of strengths. It enables effective pooling of resources (Van Summeren *et al.*, 2022): where starting initiatives lack expertise, resources and networks, they can call on others that do have these resources. By making use of their services, small local initiatives can start projects that they otherwise would not be able to because of the complexities,

associated risks and time investment needed. The models also show how knowledge, expertise and experience of energy cooperatives – as in the Netherlands and Scotland - and of third sector organisations – as in Ireland - is a valuable resource that can be mobilised in efforts to alleviate energy poverty. The Irish PPP model depends on pooling resources, acknowledging interdependencies and seeking synergies – in this case between third sector organisations with a good track record in providing support to households in energy poverty and energy suppliers that have funds available for social support for clients that have problems with paying their energy bill.

4.2.1 *Institutional support*

At the same time however, what is lacking is national policy recognition of the value that these socially innovative models provide. Such a recognition is currently absent in the Netherlands, which hampers the provision of both legislative, policy and financial support. In the Dutch context, the replication and upscaling of the service models discussed can only become successful if the institutional context becomes more conducive through targeted subsidies, through improvement of the level playing field for citizen energy communities, and by helping mobilise financial resources from large financial investors (such as pension funds). In Ireland, a similar situation is apparent. Third sector organisations with their long history, are not recognized for their value by national government, which is why they now have turned to collaborate with energy suppliers that *do* recognize that these organisations have connections and deep knowledge that they themselves lack. Time has yet to tell if and how this new relationship will last. In both Ireland and the Netherlands, there appears to be a distance between national policy ideas targeting energy poverty and local realities that ask for approaches that are better tailored and more responsive to local needs.

In the Bulgarian example, institutional transformations formed the starting point. The discussion in the example of Bulgaria was about the creation of an enabling framework, first by the adoption of a shared definition of energy poverty; and second, through an improved national governance. Both need to enable a better, more transparent and targeted use of existing resources and existing financial instruments than so far has been the case. The innovativeness of new funding mechanisms is a step forward towards offering support to households in multi-family buildings. The recognition that these funding schemes could by design improve the situation of energy vulnerable households still requires further institutional recognition and support. Hence, instead of concrete business models, the most significant development in the Bulgarian context is the institutional transformation taking place that is expected to create more favourable regulatory conditions for new governance and collaborative models, opening up space for addressing energy poverty in a more coordinated, collaborative and transparent manner.

4.2.2 *Institutional change?*

To the extent that the models discussed are or can be successfully replicated across locales, they may herald an important institutional change. The models discussed are based on normative frameworks that focus on multiple value generation, including social and human values such as decency and dignity. They do so through strengthening resilience and through engaging people in the energy transition. To the extent that these models become adopted more widespread, they may inspire policy change at national levels as well. In the

end, national policy, legislation and leadership is imperative to mobilise resources to further secure the longer-term viability of these models. For these novel models to provide multiple values to society and in particular to the alleviation of energy poverty in a sustained manner, they need to generate sufficient revenues. Hence, the financial value creation is crucial as it provides the basis for the prolonged provision of social value.

4.3 Institutional conditions and governance competences as key resources

To conclude, crucial for the governance of the models discussed – their design, management and realisation – are the actors involved, their collaborations in view of interdependent activities and the institutional context that enables these activities (Mourik *et al.*, 2021; Barnes and Haussen, 2022). Another important defining variable for the success of innovative BMs that aim to deliver multiple values, including energy poverty alleviation, lies in the evolution of constellations of actors and their cooperation. Trust and (social) contractual agreements are important here because they endorse the development of a partially shared new normative framework – away from sole commercial orientations. It is through the deployment of activities in collaboration with a variety of actors and through working with (or around) the institutional context, that a new BM can become successful. For innovative governance arrangements that address energy poverty this context is of such importance for the initiatives' operations that it can be considered a key resource. The same goes for the competences that are beneficial in navigating the institutional landscape and finding creative ways to operate within its boundaries. While the innovative capacity of the models partially lies in finding ways to work with or around institutional and other barriers, the replication, upscaling and long-term viability depends on the institutional framework adopting favourable conditions (Barnes and Hanssen, 2022). In the case of Scotland, it appears that feedback from innovative initiatives is taken into account in the improvement of national policy and legislation. Let's hope that other countries follow this example.¹⁷

¹⁷ Deliverable 3.2 will address how partners from the EnergyMeasures project have contributed to policy debates at national, regional and national levels.

Annex 1: Elements of the business model canvas

Table 8: Business model canvas elements (adapted from Keane *et al.*, 2018)

Element	Description
Customer segments	An organisation serves its value proposition(s) to one or more customer segments
Value propositions	An organisation offers a mix of products/services to create value for each customer segment
Channels	An organisation communicates and delivers its value proposition to each customer segment via various channels
Customer relationships	An organisation establishes and maintains relationships with each customer segment
Revenue streams	An organisation generates revenue streams from the delivery of value to each customer segment
Key resources	An organisation requires resources (<i>e.g.</i> , people) to create and deliver the business model elements
Key activities	An organisation performs a set of activities to create and deliver the business model elements
Key partners	An organisation may outsource some activities to its network of suppliers/partners
Cost structure	Each element of an organisation's business model has a cost component

Annex 2: Background and set-up workshop Netherlands

Focus of the workshop: exploring new models for energy communities to alleviate energy poverty

In recent years, Dutch energy cooperatives have become more interested in alleviating energy poverty. New energy community initiatives wonder how they can organise their project in such a manner that households in energy poverty can also participate (*e.g.*, in the project itself; in the cooperative; in the ownership; or in the benefits that result from the activities). Several supra-local cooperative service models have evolved over the past years that provide support to local initiatives of the type mentioned. In addition, for existing energy cooperatives, the rising energy prices have resulted in significantly increased revenues, which has triggered their commitment to use the profits for investments that help alleviate energy poverty.

Preparation of the BM workshop

Before the workshop, semi-structured as well as open Interviews were held with all participants, to learn more about each participants specific interest in the topic and to learn more about the type of business models that were relevant to discuss. We prepared various BMs, that we wanted to discuss during the workshop.

Participants included both cooperatives that had developed a model (and put it in practice to some extent) as well as cooperatives that were interested but still searching for ways to organise this. All participants were interviewed beforehand. The results presented below are based on both the preparatory work, interviews and the workshop itself.

Table 8 Interviews to prepare for or gather additional info in relation to the BM workshop

	Date	Interview held with participant:	Topic
1.	Oct. 2022	EnergieFabriek Tilburg (energy cooperative)	
2.	March 25 th 2022	Zon op alle Daken/GOED (energy cooperative)	Evolving service model to help local initiatives in developing RE projects that alleviate energy poverty
3.	October 2022	Energie van Rotterdam (energy cooperative)	Evolving service model to help local initiatives in developing RE projects that alleviate energy poverty
4.	March 10 th 2022	Deltawind (energy cooperative)	Evolving service model to re-invest revenues to alleviate energy poverty
5.	Nov. 2022	Energie bank Rotterdam (energy bank)	Activities of the Energy Bank Rotterdam and how the workshop could be of interest to them
6.	March 2022- Nov 2022	Municipality Eindhoven	Informal talks about collaborations between the municipality and energy cooperatives; and about potential interest in using the rooftops of municipal

	Date	Interview held with participant:	Topic
			real estate for collective PV rooftops – in order to then use the revenues for energy poverty alleviation
7.	Oct. 2022	Province of Zuid-Holland	Brief meet-up in online call: the role and interest of Zuid-Holland province in the workshop topic in general
8.		Bossche Windmolen	No interview beforehand

Workshop design and set-up

The business modelling workshop took place online on November 17th, 2022. Five energy cooperatives, and an Energy Bank, a municipal and provincial civil servant participated (total of 10 stakeholder participants). The business modelling workshop was organised with the aim to exchange ideas and experiences of different types of cooperatives and initiatives, with the central question as to how they can best contribute to improve solidarity in the energy transition and alleviate energy poverty and – vulnerability. The assumption was that cooperatives with this dual aim – contributing to increased installed capacity of renewable energy *and* contributing to the alleviation of energy poverty and vulnerability – need to work with a different business/organisational model compared to those that mainly focus on renewable energy generation. The following question was the point of departure:

As an energy cooperative that develops a collective solar rooftop (or a wind energy project), how can you do this in such a manner that you generate revenues that can be used to alleviate energy poverty in your neighbourhood/in the locality?

Two presentations (Deltawind and Zon-op-alle-Daken) were given, both triggering discussion among the participants. Differences between models, underlying values and challenges were discussed at length. This discussion was considered very useful and valuable by all participants (based on our evaluation afterwards). In fact, we all felt that an important conversation had started and that we should continue the conversation. A report (in Dutch) was written afterwards and shared with participants. IN addition, the results have been presented at an online conference on January 19th (organised by sister project ENPOR, in collaboration with EnergyMeasures).

Annex 3: Background and set-up workshop Bulgaria

In view of the latest policy changes to the MFAB renovation programme's second phase that propose a decrease in state funding from a 100% grant to one of 80%, a National Roundtable on Sustainable Energy Financing on March 1st 2023 was organised to discuss the two main implementation areas of the Fund – the renovation of residential and public buildings. The aim was to discuss the relevance and importance of the Fund in light of the current and future national strategic goals and policies, also considering the expected new version of the National Energy and Climate Plan. The EnergyMeasures Business Modelling workshop was organised addressing the Fund in relation to residential buildings.

Focus of the BM workshop: enabling private co-financing for home renovations

The business modelling workshop was organised to address the change from 100% towards 80% grant financing, thereby zooming in on that 20% that is to be provided by private actors. In addition, the question to be addressed was how energy poor or - vulnerable households that currently do not have any access to financial resources, can be supported to find ways to provide their co-financing obligation.

In preparation of the workshop, suggestions to develop and apply various mechanisms for these specific groups have been formulated and discussed. These included *e.g.* pay-as-you-save schemes, allocation of energy poor households eligible for increased grant rates or preferential loans by application of the new energy poverty definition, on-bill financing, etc. A BM canvas was developed by Eneffect beforehand that could be adapted based on the outcomes (or could be used to structure the discussion).

Preparation of the BM workshop

To prepare for the BM workshop, several meetings were organised with consortium partners DuneWorks, UCC, Tighean Innse Gall. In addition, several formal and informal interviews were helpful to further delineate the focus of the workshops and to anticipate various stakeholder perspectives.

Table 9: Interviews to prepare for or gather additional info in relation to the BM workshop

	Date	Interview held with (stakeholder name)	Interview topics:
1.	26.09.22	Marko Markov, Econoler	The role of the National Decarbonisation Fund and its market readiness
2.	26.09.22	Dochka Vassileva, Fund of Funds	Available financial resources in support of the upcoming National renovation programmes
3.	14.11.22	Kamelia Georgieva, National Trust EcoFund	Upcoming energy efficiency project and innovative financial solutions by the Fund
4.	21.11.22	Talk with Anton Ivanov, Bulgarian Energy and Mining Forum	Energy crisis and RES projects' potential
5.	29.11.22	Discussion with members of Energy Agency Plovdiv, Greenpeace, SOFENA, Center for the Study of Democracy, ZaZemiata, Black Sea Research Centre during the National	Energy poverty, one-stop-shops, energy communities

	Date	Interview held with (stakeholder name)	Interview topics:
		Conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies	
6.	20.01.23	Discussion meeting with stakeholders from the Working Group of SMAFIN and BeSMART projects	Keynote speakers and discussion questions for the workshop; important policy developments; ministries to be involved

Workshop design and set-up

Envisaged participants: key stakeholders as the Energy Efficiency and Energy Poverty Commission at the National Green Deal Council, SEDA, AEE, EcoEnergy, BACIW, Habitat Bulgaria, municipal representatives, energy agencies and auditors, construction sector representatives, financial institutions, energy services providers, energy experts

The presentations by key actors as Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, Bulgarian Construction Chamber, BACC, Center for Study of Democracy were followed by a discussion based on the following questions:

- What is the interest to the first stage of the national renovation programme and which are the first identified barriers from the perspective of the national authorities?
- What is the feedback from the municipalities and the homeowners' associations?
- What are the attitudes towards the second stage of the programme requiring co-financing from the homeowners?
- Are there financial mechanisms in place to secure the co-financing, including from vulnerable / energy-poor households?

The workshop took place on March 1st 2023, and during that session on energy poverty alleviation, there were over 100 participants online and in person, with representatives from the Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, specialized and public funds, local authorities and NGOs.

Annex 4: Background and set-up workshop Ireland

General background

The third sector in Ireland is quite dynamic and actors within the sector occupy numerous roles ranging from service provision to advocacy and campaign work. Therefore, the Irish partners were keen to engage with as many of the different actors as possible focused on addressing energy poverty in Ireland.

Preparation of the BM workshop

The Irish process on business model comprised a series direct engagements culminating in BM workshop in which a range of state actors and voluntary organisations were engaged. This approach had two complimentary dimensions to it: both in further refining the innovative business model that Energy Action was developing in partnership with several of Ireland's energy providers; but also to gauge the levels of understanding and commitment those approached see the issue of energy poverty and how it should be addressed. These actors included:

- *Dublin City Council*, local government authority.
- *South Dublin County Council*, local government authority.
- *Cork City Council*, the authority responsible for local government in the city of Cork.
- *Carbery Housing Association*, a charitable housing association based in Cork.
- *NCE Energy Hub*, which helps homes and businesses become more energy efficient in the Cork area.
- *The Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (MABS)*, the Irish money advice service.
- *Threshold*, independent advice and advocacy service tackling homelessness in Ireland.
- *Climote*, a remote heating service company.
- *Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI)*.
- *SSE Airtricity*, Irish utility company supplying electricity / gas to business & residential customers.
- *Electric Ireland*, Irish utility company supplying electricity / gas to business & residential customers.
- *ESB Networks*, which builds, operates and maintains the electricity network in Ireland.
- *Commission for the Regulation of Utilities (CRU)*, energy and water economic utility regulator.
- *ALONE*, a charity organisation in Ireland advocating on behalf of older people living alone.
- *Think-tank for Action on Social Change (TASC)*, public education charity and independent think-tank.
- *St. Vincent de Paul Society (SVP) Ireland*, a voluntary network dedicated to tackling poverty.
- *Daughters of Charity*, community of religious looking to address poverty, including energy poverty.

Resulting from these efforts, a number of third sector actors were invited to participate in the BM workshop with a view to sharing insights and lessons learned from their engagements with their respective clients. The

workshop organisers followed up with a series of asynchronous dialogues with those were not able to attend on the day.

The workshop took place on January 30, 2023. Participants included:

- Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (MABS), the Irish money advice service. ALONE, a charity organisation in Ireland advocating on behalf of older people living alone.
- The Think-tank for Action on Social Change (TASC), a public education charity and independent think-tank looking to address inequality and sustain democracy by engaging in research and public outreach.
- The St. Vincent de Paul Society (SVP) Ireland, an international Christian voluntary network dedicated to tackling poverty in all its forms.
- Energy Action.

Table 10: Interviews undertaken in preparation for or to gather additional information in relation to the BM workshop

	Date	Interview held with (stakeholder name)	Interview topics:
1.	Q3 & Q4 2022	Dublin City Council	Household engagement potential and examining existing structures designed to alleviate energy poverty
2.	Q3 & Q4 2022	South Dublin County Council	
3.	Q3 & Q4 2022	Cork City Council	
4.	Q3 2022	Carbery Housing Association	
5.	Q1 & Q2 2022	NCE Energy Hub	
6.	Q2, Q3 & Q4 2022	The Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (MABS)	
7.	Q2 2022	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI)	
8.	Q3 & Q4 2022	SSE Airtricity	
9.	Q3 & Q4 2022	Electric Ireland	
10.	Q2 2022	Commission for the Regulation of Utilities (CRU)	
11.	Q3 & Q4 2022	ALONE	
12.	Q3 & Q4 2022	Think-tank for Action on Social Change (TASC)	
13.	Q3 & Q4 2022	St. Vincent de Paul Society (SVP) Ireland	
14.	Q3 & Q4 2022	The Daughters of Charity	
15.	Q3 & Q4 2022	Climote	

Workshop design and set-up

To minimise the travel burden on participants, the majority of whom are based in Dublin, the workshop was hosted in the Dublin offices of the Monetary and Budgetary Advice Service (MABS). Participants were informed that all conversations within the workshop would be kept in strict confidence and that the workshop organisers would be guided by the outcomes and flow of the discussion. These discussions were broken down into themes, focusing on the different scales of action their organisations' business models engaged with; from the national structural level, to the short- and medium-term policy cycles, to immediate day-to-day barriers each organisation faces. These discussions were stimulated using the following three questions, with discussions guided back to the topic by the organisers if needed.

Question 1: How do we address the structural and physical conditions of energy poverty?

Question 2: What can we do (in the short and medium term) to address energy poverty?

Question 3: How is your organisation working to meet the challenge of energy poverty and what are the key challenges you face implementing it?

Attendance and evaluation by participants

Each of the participants from the six organisations attending the workshop (or the follow-up asynchronous dialogues) recognised the value of the workshop and were given an opportunity to learn from the experiences and approaches taken by the other participants.

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